

<https://www.archer2.ac.uk>

2nd GPU eCSE Call

- Apply for funding for RSEs to work on research software development
- Must target accelerated architectures
- Any research remit, any architecture
- Can fund local RSE or you can request an ARCHER2 expert
- Closing date: 17 Sep 2024

<https://www.archer2.ac.uk/ecse/calls/>

Image credit: Dr Mattia Almansi

Access to compute resources

- Driving Test: Free test access for anyone working at a UK academic institution
- Pump Priming: Free test access for EPSRC-remit work
- Via UKRI: access for EPSRC and NERC remit research
- Via EPCC: access for commercial organisations
- If you want access, get in touch!

<https://www.archer2.ac.uk/support-access/access.html>

Training and training materials

- Free online and in person courses
- Access to training material online
- Materials open source to allow others to build on them
- Collaborative development of training materials – let us know if you want to work with us
- Get in touch if you want us to come and run training at your location

<https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/>

Outreach

- Aim to reach young people from diverse backgrounds and those under-represented in higher education
- Prioritise activities to improve social mobility
- Make outreach materials freely available for others to use

<https://discover.epcc.ed.ac.uk/>

EPSRC
and NERC

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